

Studies on oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes of Schiff bases derived from pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazine and pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide with salicylaldehyde

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Oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes of Schiff bases (L and L') derived respectively from pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide and pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide with salicylaldehyde have been prepared. The Schiff bases behave as terdentate O (enolic) N (azomethine) O (phenolic) donors in their fully deprotonated complexes; bidentate O (keto) N (azomethine) donors in the hydroxo complexes and bidentate O (enolic) N (azomethine) donor in the partially deprotonated complex, $(UO_2)_2(acac)_2(L'-2H)$.

There is growing interest^{1,2} on the chemistry of hydrazones derived from acid hydrazides and aldehydes/ketones due to their structural, biological and analytical significance. While metal complexes of the hydrazones derived from many aliphatic, aromatic and heteroaromatic systems have been synthesized^{2,3}, little study has been reported^{4,5} on hydrazones containing pyrazine ring system. Pyrazine with two ring nitrogens and hydrazone moieties at its 2- or 2,3-positions exhibits several bonding possibilities and might produce complexes with interesting structural features.

The present work is concerned with synthesis and study on the nature of bonding in oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes with hydrazones (L and L') derived from pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide and pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide with salicylaldehyde.

Vanadium is receiving considerable attention as a biologically important metal due to the existence of vanadoenzyme⁶. Dioxouranium(VI) complexes are of structural interest due to varied geometry they assume. Dioxouranium(VI) complexes are said to have possible applications in solar energy conversion system owing to spectral and excited state electron-transfer properties of the UO_2^{2+} ion⁷.

Results and Discussion

The oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes are brown and red, respectively. Molar conductance values ($26-41 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMSO ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the complexes **1**, **2**, **5-7** are less for 1 : 1 electrolytes suggesting⁸ their non-electrolytic nature despite some solvolysis; complexes **3**, **4** and **8** show the values in the range $\sim 70-80 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for 1 : 2 electrolyte types.

Infrared spectrum of the free hydrazone ligand L shows

bands at 1660, 1610, 1510 and 1010 and that of L' at 1680, 1615, 1515 and 1030 cm^{-1} , tentatively assigned to amide I $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$, amide II + ν_{C-O} (phenolic), and ν_{N-N} , respectively. In complexes **1**, **2**, **5** and **6**, the absence of $\nu_{C=O}$ band and large shift ($\Delta\nu \sim 50-60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the strong $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the $C=N-N=C$ group resulting from coordination through deprotonated enolised oxygen; new bands at 1330–1340 cm^{-1} assignable⁹ to ν_{NCO} support enolisation. Positive shifts in the ν_{N-N} ($\Delta\nu \sim 20-30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as well as ν_{C-O} (phenolic) ($\Delta\nu \sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands relative to the free ligand values suggest^{2,9} coordination through azomethine nitrogen and deprotonated phenolic oxygen in the complexes. Proton NMR signals due to OH (phenolic) and NH at δ 12.63 and 11.27 of the Schiff base L are absent in complex **2**, supporting deprotonation. Downfield shift of the proton signal due to $-CH=N-$ for **2** from the free ligand (δ 9.29) suggests coordination through the azomethine nitrogen to uranium.

Complexes **1**, **5**, **6** and **8** exhibit broad bands at $\sim 3000-3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to their hydrated nature; mass loss (4.5% found, 5.53% calcd.) suffered by **1** under isothermal ($110-120^\circ$) heating (1 h) in an air suggests water is crystalline while little-loss occurring for **5**, **6** and **8** may suggest, though inconclusively¹⁰, water is coordinated. In complexes **3**, **4** and **8** $\nu_{C=O}$ band remains almost stationary at their free ligand positions with, however, significant reduction in intensity, suggesting keto-oxygen coordination; no new band due to ν_{NCO^-} around $\sim 1330-1340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is apparent, unlike complexes **1** and **2**. Presence of phenolic OH and NH proton signals in the NMR spectra of **4** and **8** and at about the same positions (δ 12.64–12.69 and 11.32–11.10 ppm) as in the free ligand indicate that neither groups are deprotonated or involved in coordination to the metal. Positive shifts ($\Delta\nu$ 15–25 cm^{-1}) in the ν_{N-N} band in **3**, **4** and **8**

suggest coordination through azomethine nitrogen. Complexes **3** and **4** are dimers (from molecular weight measurements), possibly hydroxo-bridged; a new band at 550–570 cm^{-1} may be assigned¹¹ to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations of the μ -hydroxo bridges.

Compounds $[\text{MO}_n(\text{acac})_2]$ ($\text{M}, n = \text{V}, 1; \text{U}, 2$) have been reported¹² to be good starting materials for synthesis of their complexes. $\text{UO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ in course of its reaction with L' suffers partial displacement of acac moiety to give $(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{acac})_2(\text{L}'\cdot 2\text{H})$ (complex **7**) whose IR data indicate as above in **5** and **6**, coordinates through deprotonated enolised oxygen and azomethine nitrogen of the Schiff base. Bands ~ 1440 and ~ 1390 cm^{-1} are attributable to the deformation and bending modes of methyl groups of the acac moiety. Proton signals observed at δ 2.2–2.3 and 5.68–5.84 ppm in the NMR spectrum of **7** may be assigned¹² respectively to CH_3 and CH of the deprotonated acetylacetonate moiety. Bands attributable to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ for the complexes are not discernible. In all the complexes, strong bands characteristic of *trans*- UO_2 and VO groups are observed respectively in at $\sim 880, 920$ and $970\text{--}980$ cm^{-1} in agreement with the literature reports¹³.

Magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values (1.63–1.53 B.M. per vanadium) at room temperature for the oxovanadium(IV) complexes are a little lower than the spin-only moment for one unpaired electron. The spin-only moment for isolated V^{IV} ions may be reduced through spin-orbit coupling or exchange coupling between metal centres. However, spin-orbit coupling in almost all V^{IV} complexes is efficiently quenched so that lowering of magnetic moment usually indicates antiferromagnetic coupling between the vanadium centres¹⁴.

EPR spectra of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes in polycrystalline state at room temperature are nearly isotropic with the g -values close to 1.96 like the one for VO (imino-diacetate) with $\text{VO}(\text{ONO})$ coordination environment¹⁵. These g -values are lower than those for oxovanadium(IV)- β -diketone, -salen complexes, indicating less covalent bonding through the bonded atoms to the $\text{V}=\text{O}$ moiety¹⁶. No half-field transition has been located in the polycrystalline solids at room temperature (in absence of EPR study at low temperature and/or variable temperature magnetic measurements, occurrence of subnormal magnetic moments is difficult to ascertain).

Electronic spectra (nujol) of the oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes are characterized by broad bands at 405–450 nm which are generally not much shifted in DMSO; molar extinction coefficients ($\epsilon = 3240\text{--}1200$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) of the bands suggest that they are charge transfer (LMCT) in origin, the typical band of UO_2^{2+} expected¹⁷ around 390–450 nm is perhaps buried underneath the broad envelope. An additional band observed at 570–600 nm for the oxovanadium(IV) complexes may be assigned¹⁸ to ${}^2B_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2B_1(d_{x^2-y^2})$ transition.

From analytical, IR and NMR spectral data, the Schiff bases appear to behave terdentate coordinating through azomethine-N and deprotonated enol-O and phenol-O in complexes **1, 2, 5** and **6** which may assume 5-/6-coordinate geometry (or higher (U)) using, besides vanadyl/uranyl oxygens, water and/or other centres from neighbouring molecules in the crystal lattice; coordinate geometry in complexes **3, 4** and **8** is attained through keto-O and azomethine-N of the Schiff bases, the bridging hydroxo groups and the vanadyl/uranyl oxygens (Fig. 1), and in complex **7** though deprotonated enol-O and azomethine-N

Fig. 1

of L' , two oxygens of deprotonated acac moiety and two *trans*-uranyl oxygens (Fig. 2). Without crystallographic analysis, however, the structures are not unambiguous.

Fig. 2

Experimental

Ligands salicylaldehyde-2-pyrazinoyl hydrazone (**L**) and bis(salicylaldehyde)-2,3-pyrazinoyldihydrazone (**L'**) were prepared according the reported procedures⁴.

$\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{UO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ethanolic solution of vanadyl chloride (pH $\sim 3\text{--}4$) as well as an acetone solution of uranyl chloride were prepared as described¹⁹. Uranium trioxide, vanadium pentoxide and uranyl acetate used were of E. Merck/B.D.H. make.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$VO(L-2H).H_2O$ (1) and $UO_2(L-2H)$ (2) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 1, 15.50 (15.69), 2, 46.20 (46.67)) were obtained by refluxing (1–2 h) on a steam-bath a mixed solution (20 ml) containing the respective metal acetylacetonate and the ligand in the solvent indicated (1 and 2 mmol; ethanol for 1) and (0.277 and 0.578 mmol; methanol for 2), and filtering the precipitates formed.

$(VO)_2L_2(OH)_2Cl_2$ (3) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 13.20 (14.11), Cl : 9.45 (9.82); mol. wt., Found (Calcd.), 705 (723)) was prepared by refluxing (1 h) on a steam-bath a solution containing vanadyl chloride (~2 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) and the ligand (~1 mmol) in 1,2-dichloroethane (30 ml), concentrating, and adding diethyl ether to the chilled solution to provide brown crystals which were then filtered.

$(UO_2)_2L_2(OH)_2Cl_2$ (4) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 43.12 (42.16), Cl : 7.05 (6.29); mol. wt. Found (Calcd.), 1149 (1129)) was obtained as a red compound on refluxing (1–2 h) a mixture of uranyl chloride (0.349 mmol) in acetone (15 ml) and the ligand (0.702 mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml) and filtering the precipitated mass.

$(VO)_2(L'-4H).2H_2O$ (5) and $(UO_2)_2(acac)_2(L'-2H)$ (7) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 5, 18.90 (17.89), 7, 41.13 (41.75)) were prepared by refluxing (1–2 h) on a steam-bath a mixture of the respective metal acetylacetonate and the ligand (0.490 and 0.495 mmol) in 1,2-dichloroethane (20 ml) and acetone (50 ml) for 5, and (0.257 and 0.247 mmol) in acetone (10 ml) and acetone (20 ml) plus carbon tetrachloride (10 ml) for 7, and filtering off the crystalline mass produced upon concentration.

$(UO_2)_2(L'-4H).4H_2O$ (6) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 46.40 (47.03)) was obtained as a red compound when a mixture of $UO_2(CH_3COO)_2.2H_2O$ (1 mmol) in methanol (25 ml) and the ligand (1 mmol) in acetone (75 ml) refluxed (4 h) on a steam-bath, then concentrated (1/4 vol), cooled and stirred with a little ether to precipitate the compound which was filtered.

$(UO_2)_2L'(OH)_2Cl_2.4H_2O$ (8) (Found (Calcd.), M% : 40.25 (42.46), Cl: 5.66 (6.33)) was obtained as a red compound when a solution of uranyl chloride (0.349 mmol) in acetone (15 ml) mixed with a solution of the ligand (0.371 mmol) in the same solvent (30 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath (2 h), then concentrated (1/2 vol) and cooled to obtain the precipitate which was filtered.

In all preparation the filtered mass was isolated after washing with appropriate solvent and drying over fused $CaCl_2$. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. Infrared spectra (KBr) and electronic spectra (nujol/DMSO) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1330 and Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometers, respectively. C, H, N were analysed at Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata. EPR spectra in the X-band region were obtained from R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Chennai and R.S.I.C., Bose

Institute, Kolkata. 1H HMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) were recorded at the Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata. Metals and halogen were analysed gravimetrically²⁰. Magnetic moment and conductivity were measured as described elsewhere⁴. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected²¹ for temperature independent paramagnetism using a value of 50×10^{-6} cgs units. Molecular weight was measured by Rast's method²² using diphenyl as solvent.

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